

APPEAL OF THE ALLEA GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN SUPPORT OF UKRAINIAN SCIENCE

**Adopted by the delegates of the 2026 ALLEA General Assembly
held in Warsaw, Poland, on 28 May 2026**

This Appeal reaffirms and underscores the [ten-point Action Plan](#) adopted in Warsaw, Poland, on 2 June 2022 by the leadership of the Polish Academy of Sciences, the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, the U.S. National Academy of Sciences, the German National Academy of Sciences Leopoldina, the Royal Danish Academy of Sciences and Letters, the Royal Society of the United Kingdom, and the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (ALLEA). Issued four years after its adoption, this document reiterates the continued relevance and urgency of the commitments undertaken in support of Ukrainian science.

ALLEA notes that Ukrainian science continues to develop despite the ongoing Russian aggression, under conditions of extreme pressure and uncertainty. This aggression poses serious risks to researchers, research institutions, and scientific infrastructure. ALLEA once again expresses its full solidarity with and unwavering support for its member, the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine.

As part of the ALLEA General Assembly, a special satellite event entitled ***Supporting the Ukrainian Research Ecosystem through International Exchange and Collaboration*** was convened. The event addressed the challenges faced by Ukrainian science as a result of the ongoing war and explored pathways to overcome them. Participants emphasised that the preservation, restoration, and further development of the Ukrainian research ecosystem are essential to ensuring the country's long-term prosperity, resilience, and sovereignty.

In this context, ALLEA strongly urges global leaders and funding bodies, when designing recovery and financial assistance programmes for Ukraine, to prioritise the rebuilding of a modern, resilient, and globally integrated research system as a cornerstone of national recovery.

The **actions** outlined below provide examples of practical steps that can be undertaken by scientific communities within ALLEA member academies and by partners worldwide to support Ukrainian science:

- ❖ **Facilitating the involvement of Ukrainian scientists** in cooperation with leading international research centres and supporting their participation in large-scale international projects and grant programmes.
- ❖ **Establishing joint centres of excellence** in key scientific fields.
- ❖ **Donating second-hand research equipment**, when upgrading or renewing experimental infrastructure, to institutes of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine with specific and urgent needs.
- ❖ **Creating funding programmes for joint research conducted by international teams**, including researchers working in Ukraine, and enabling joint academic appointments. Targeted grant support aimed at preserving Ukraine's scientific environment is essential for sustaining and developing the country's research potential.
- ❖ **Establishing and supporting networks of Ukrainian scholars** working in Europe and beyond.
- ❖ **Developing dedicated funding programmes for early-career researchers** from Ukraine and their teams, including those operating under remote working arrangements.
- ❖ **Providing Ukrainian researchers with access to specialised research facilities abroad.**
- ❖ **Launching long-term bilateral cooperation programmes between the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine and ALLEA member academies**, extending beyond dedicated calls and projects within the EU Horizon Europe framework.
- ❖ **Conducting reciprocal assessments of research ecosystems in Ukraine and other ALLEA member academies** to identify best practices and opportunities for sustainable cooperation.

ALLEA reaffirms its commitment to supporting Ukrainian science and calls upon the international academic community, policymakers, and funding organisations to act collectively and decisively in safeguarding Ukraine's scientific future as an integral part of Europe's shared intellectual and cultural heritage.

About ALLEA

Established in 1994, ALLEA serves as the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, advocating for the role of science as a global public good and promoting interdisciplinary collaboration among its Member Academies and beyond.

ALLEA promotes science and research in Europe and globally, and provides a forum for scientific exchange across borders, thereby consolidating the collective voice of European academia and contributing a European perspective to international discourse. As such, ALLEA is widely recognised as renowned academic stakeholder at the European science-policy-society interface and is frequently consulted as a trusted source of expertise for policymakers, media and the public.

A charitable non-profit association formally registered as All European Academies (ALLEA) e.V. under German law, ALLEA has its own legal personality and remains fully independent of political, religious, and commercial interests.

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